

COMPLETE ACTIVITY ANALYSIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT ASSET THEORY

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ABSTRACT

It is devoted to problems describing the aspects related to the comparative analysis of fixed asset analysis, the method of forming fixed asset, the full use of fixed asset in the business unit and the management of the asset, and the management models of fixed assets. As a result of the type of economic change that is growing in the country, significant changes are occurring, and in turn, the globalization of Uzbekistan is increasing its impact on the economy. As a result, the influence of the joint venture capital and other economic joint ventures on capital value and working capital is changing.

In the context of the globalization of the economy, an active economic entity is recognized as an economic profit generator. Aktivlap expands the activity of the economic entity and allows you to get a profit, which is very important for future development. Assets is a type of economic category and is directly involved in the production, development and production products.

As a result of the type of economic growth that is growing in the country, significant differences are being observed, and in turn, the globalization of Uzbekistan is increasing its impact on the economy. As a result, joint-stock companies, joint-stock companies and other economic joint ventures have increased their influence on the capital value and working capital of joint-stock companies.

In the context of the globalization of the economy, an active economic entity is recognized as an economic profit generator. Assets expands the activity of the economic entity and allows you to get a profit, which is very important for future development. Assets is a type of economic category and is directly involved in the production, development and production products.

A.A.Karimov, A.K.Ibragimov, N.K.Rizaev, N.M.Imamova's book «Financial assets that are produced, consumed or turned into profit during the normal operating cycle (revenue-material savings and debit (such as a cap) includes an asset, even if the asset cannot be converted into a product within twelve months of the reporting period. Total assets include assets held for trading (for example, financial assets that meet the definition of assets held for trading in the 9th Con. 73) and the total amount of long-term financial assets» [3].

According to I. Icmánov, «In the practice of accounting, the capital involved in the activity of the economic entity is called an asset, and in the process of capitalization, it is divided into fixed assets (working capital) and fixed assets (working capital)» [4].

In carrying out development, improving product quality, increasing competitiveness and expanding the scope of production, it serves to increase the position of a long-term asset in the activity of an economic entity. The balance sheet includes fixed assets, intangible assets, capital investments, long-term investments, fixed assets, capital investments, long-term debits and deferred income.

Depending on the form of ownership, it is necessary to have funds at a staged level in order to carry out business activities. In the calculation of the total assets of the economic entity, the fixed assets occupy a high position. Fixed assets are considered as one of the most productive funds in the activity of the economic entity due to its reliability and quick profitability.

The total asset of the economic entity, excluding the long-term asset, is fully consumed in the cycle of production, transfers its value to the product, and is restored both in material-type reproduction and in value description, and it is always in stock.

In order to ensure the consistency of production, it is necessary to pay attention to the pecypclap, which is common in the construction of an economic unit, as well as to the accumulation of dirt from the surface. Otherwise, the liquidity of the fund will decrease and the production line will be damaged. The degree of participation in the development of a public asset and the level of involvement in it can also be determined by the source of formation. In carrying out the activities of the business entity, the fixed assets can be classified according to the type designation. According to it, the liquidity of public assets, the participation of public assets in development, the solvency of public assets, the source of formation of public assets, and the level of risk in assessing the solvency of public assets were classified. Economic relations play an important role in the activity of the economic sector. Due to the fact that the sourcing, development, shipping and distribution of the product is carried out.

Economic relations are carried out by correspondence. As a result, one economic entity is the supplier of material resources, a provider of work and a provider of services, and the second economic entity is a producer and consumer. As a result, this valuer will have the right and obligation to pay the value of the work and service. The precise organization of the negotiations resulting from such a relationship will ensure the rapid transformation of the assets and the timely arrival of the funds. Due to the full use of fixed assets in the activity of the economic enterprise, it is possible to reduce the cost of the product, increase the profit and improve the profitability. Bipoq by japiy directly depends on how to form the active file and use the file. Shy cababli by cohada is very important to improve the analysis and patient performance. It should be detailed in terms of the development of the total assets of the business entity and the performance of accounting functions. The development function ensures the completeness of the production of the active substance, and the transformation of the tissue from the round shape to the pile shape according to the myomala function.

The effectiveness of the development of the economic unit, the organization of development in the map depends on the level of provision of the final assets. Due to the

shortage of active labor in the product development industry, it can affect the intensity, consistency and duration of the production, and eventually it can become unsustainable. With Shy and Bip, the optical protection of the active lens from the eye will lead to inefficient use of the lens. It depends on the production tools and business processes of the company. The means of production consists of labor facilities and capital (including VAT) as well as unfinished production, work-in-process capital, short-term financial investments, capital in the accounts (debit book), raw materials, production of goods and services, and other products.

It is possible to multiply the structure of the economic activity in our country based on the development of the invention of the production equipment, the development of the production equipment, the development of the production equipment, and the production of the production equipment. The quality and uniqueness of the product, the demand for the product, the financial situation, the material and technical support, the supply of goods and the settlement with the supplier, the price of the product, the natural and climatic conditions, and other factors influence the change in the production of the assets used in the production of the farm. multiplies.

Multi-classifying a public asset to a specific bip tag allows you to create a separate public asset that is easier to create and then manage in the public asset type category. Depending on the location of the manufacturing plant in the production plant or in the functional area, the plant plant is divided into the fixed assets of the plant and the circulating assets involved in the production plant.

The imbalance in the supply of these assets may lead to a shortage of labor (raw materials, fuel, spare parts, etc.), which in turn will force the production of goods.

It is necessary to meet the needs in stages based on the size and arrangement of the total assets in the enterprise. The minimum level of active ingredients requires that the consistency of the ingredients in the product development is a step-by-step process.

Similarly, based on the inventive arrangement of the active layer, the method of further increasing the rotation efficiency of the element with the highest value in the active layer and the strategy of using the layer will be developed. One of the most important tasks in the management of public assets is to learn how to classify them according to different characteristics, and to accept different types of assets. Tayyop mahcyotlap cotilisi turns into a white pyl fund.

In the context of modernization of the economy, it is possible to raise the cost of production as a means of forming a permanent asset in the productive economic sector (Figure 1). In this widely used method, bank credit is also widely used, which is an important factor of attracting financial investment in the current economic environment, along with the raw materials and equipment found in the economic unit itself. In the same way, in most of the commercial enterprises operating in Uzbekistan, there is also a competitive edge in the formation of the production budget in the interaction with the supplier of goods. This situation can lead to serious consequences for the economic entity. By the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022, in the State Document PF-60, «On the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 cohacini further brewing dactypini the task of development» is defined.

Figure 1. The source of formation of active assets in the economy ¹

In order to determine the source of formation of a fixed asset, its own working capital is considered as its primary source, that is, the source of own funds of an economic enterprise is primarily a source of covering its long-term assets, and the remaining part is considered to cover its fixed assets. In addition, it is possible to form the financial assets of the economic entity in the account of the bank account, account of the bank account and other sources. It is necessary to form the total assets of the economic entity as much as possible into the capital account. In order to support the development of the country's industrial machinery and to increase the source of the formation of public assets, a lot of funds and funds are being issued.

In other countries, it is necessary to develop a method of closing the bank, to ensure the smooth operation of the economic unit of the company, in turn, to ensure the liquidity and solvency of the company, and to manipulate the company. In keeping with the above-mentioned idea and concept, the business owner requires the full use of the assets and the proper management of the land. For this reason, the model of management of the assets of the business enterprise is divided into 4 key areas, based on the following:

Development plan - undeveloped development plan, development of cutting plan;

Investment fund - short-term financial investment, short-term investment and other types of investment;

Supply chain - determination of the need for labor goods, procurement of stock, sending to production and other aspects of management;

Product Sourcing Process - Identifying the demand for cutting material, uploading, shipping, and other aspects of the process. In this paper, there is a detailed analysis of the inventory of fixed assets, the amount of funds, the source of fixed assets, the amount of working capital, the amount of working capital, the amount of pick-up, the amount of

¹ The author is a developer.

inventory, the amount of error prevention, the amount of assets, the amount of assets, the turnover and the pentability. It's not in accordance with what needs to be done. A modern approach is required in the organization of a different analysis of the current asset, based on the complexity of the development of the marketing plan and the unique nature of the business unit in this area. It is desirable to develop the Shy cababli ylap in the form of a sequence hapakatlap.

In our opinion, in order to ensure the continuity of the development of the production process, the first step of the business enterprise is to develop a strategy for the formation of public assets and management of the use of water in the future.

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